

REDESIGN OF THE MIXED-MODE BENDING TEST FOR DELAMINATION TOUGHNESS

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ABSTRACT

The mixed-mode bending (MMB) test uses a lever to simultaneously apply mode I and mode II loading to a split-beam specimen. A nonlinear, iterative analysis that accurately predicts the measured load-displacement response and the strain energy release rate, G , of an MMB test, has shown that the errors in G calculated using linear theory can be quite large. Because it would be inconvenient to use a nonlinear analysis to analyze MMB data, the MMB apparatus was redesigned to minimize the nonlinearity. The nonlinear analysis was used as a guide in redesigning the MMB apparatus. With the redesigned apparatus, loads are applied through a roller attached to the lever and loaded just above the midplane of the test specimen. The redesigned MMB apparatus has geometric nonlinearity errors of less than 3%, even for materials substantially tougher than APC2 (AS4/PEEK). This apparatus was demonstrated by measuring the mixed-mode delamination fracture toughness of APC2. The data from the redesigned MMB apparatus were analyzed with a linear analysis which yielded results similar to those found with the original apparatus and the nonlinear analysis.

1. INTRODUCTION

Delamination continues to be one of the major problems limiting the use of composite materials in primary structures. A major step toward predicting delamination is characterizing a material's delamination fracture toughness. Delamination fracture toughness is often expressed in terms of the critical strain energy release rate, G_c , corresponding to delamination growth.

Many tests have been used to measure fracture toughness. The double cantilever beam (DCB) test[1] is most often used to measure mode I (opening) delamination fracture toughness. The end-notched flexure (ENF) test[2] is most often used to measure mode II (sliding shear) delamination fracture toughness. However, delamination in structures is usually not a result of pure mode I or pure mode II loading, so it is important that the delamination fracture toughness be known for mixed-mode loading.

As discussed in reference 3, the mixed-mode bending (MMB) test seems to solve many of the problems encountered by other tests which have been used to measure delamination fracture toughness under mixed-mode loading. The MMB test uses a lever to simultaneously apply DCB and ENF type loadings, and by varying the lever length, practically any mode I/mode II ratio can be obtained. In addition, the MMB test can be analyzed using simple beam theory equations developed for the DCB and ENF tests, and this analysis can be used to separate the mode I and mode II components. Furthermore, delamination growth is stable for most MMB test configurations and the mixed-mode ratio stays essentially constant during delamination growth.

However, when the MMB test was used with a tough material such as APC2 (AS4/PEEK), rather large displacements were observed. These large displacements caused geometric nonlinearities. In reference 4 a nonlinear, iterative analysis was used to show that the error caused by calculating G using linear theory could be as large as 30%. This paper introduces a redesigned MMB test apparatus that minimizes this nonlinearity error.

The MMB apparatus was redesigned to reduce the nonlinearity because it would be inconvenient to use a nonlinear analysis to analyze the MMB data. The nonlinear analysis developed in reference 4 was used to optimize the redesigned MMB apparatus. This redesigned apparatus was demonstrated by measuring the fracture toughness of APC2. The results are compared to a previous study which used the original apparatus.

2. MMB TEST PROCEDURE

The MMB apparatus used in previous studies is shown in figure 1. Load is applied to a split-beam specimen by means of a lever where the distance, c , between the load-point and the fulcrum can be varied. The mode I and mode II loadings are applied simultaneously to the split-beam specimen using this lever. The downward load applied at the fulcrum of the lever produces a mode II loading similar to the ENF test. The upward load at the end of the lever creates a mode I loading similar to the DCB test. By changing loading point on the lever, and therefore the length c , the ratio of mode I to mode II loading can be changed. Load points were chosen to produce G_I/G_{II} ratios of 4/1, 1/1, and 1/4. Tests were also conducted under pure mode II where the lever was loaded directly above the center roller resulting in 3 point bending and under pure mode I where the lever was removed and the top hinge was pulled upward as in the DCB test.

The material used in this study was APC2 (made by ICI-Fiberite Co.), a tough thermoplastic composite made of AS4 fibers in a PEEK (polyetheretherketone) matrix. The longitudinal modulus, E_{11} , was measured in flexure to be 129 GPa (18.7 Msi) using a 3-point bend test with a 7.6 cm (3 in.) span length. The transverse modulus, E_{22} , and shear modulus, G_{12} , were found from the literature to be 10.1 GPa (1.46 Msi) and 5.5 GPa (0.8 Msi), respectively[3].

Unidirectional 24-ply test specimens were produced from two 15 cm x 30 cm (6"x12") panels. The specimen length was 15 cm (6 in.); the width, b , was 2.54 cm (1 in.); and the nominal thickness, h , was 3 mm (0.12 in.). Each specimen contained a 13 μ m (0.5 mil) thick Kapton delamination starter which was 6.4 cm (2.5 in.) long and placed at one end of the specimen

between the 12th and 13th plies. Hinges were bonded to the specimen as shown in figure 1 so that the initial delamination length, a , was 2.5 cm (1 in.). The half-span length, L , of each test was 5 cm (2 in.).

Each specimen was precracked to a delamination length of approximately 3.2 cm (1.25 in.) using a 4/1 mixed-mode ratio loading to be consistent with previous tests[3]. The specimens were then reloaded in displacement control at a rate of 1.27 mm/min (0.05 in/min) at the lever loading point. The load-displacement response was recorded during each fracture toughness test and the maximum load was used as the critical load in the calculation of fracture toughness, G_c . The delamination length, a , was determined during the test by observing the edge of the specimen through a 7x microscope. The edge of the specimen was coated with a white, water soluble typewriter correction fluid to increase the visibility of the delamination.

3. SOURCES OF NONLINEARITY

In reference 3, a finite element analysis, and a modified beam theory analysis, were shown to predict the load-displacement curve of the MMB test quite well at low load levels where the curve is linear. However, at higher loads required when testing tough materials such as APC2, there is some nonlinearity evident in the load-displacement curves before delamination onset. The dimensions of the specimen were chosen so that specimen nonlinearity would be negligible for both the DCB[5] and ENF[6] tests. Since the MMB test is simply a combination of these tests, the specimen nonlinearity should be small in this case as well. Similarly, since material nonlinearity was not observed in the pure mode tests, it should not be present in the MMB test. Therefore, the primary cause of the observed nonlinearity is believed to be geometric nonlinearity produced by the loading apparatus. The APC2 tests had a nonlinear response when loaded in the original MMB apparatus primarily because the loading on the apparatus changed direction as the specimen deformed. The lever was loaded by a roller, and when the lever rotated as the system was loaded, the loading direction changed so that it was always normal to the lever as seen in figure 2.

Figure 1.- MMB test apparatus

Figure 2.- Lever loading on rotated lever

4. ANALYSIS

A nonlinear analysis was developed in reference 4 to study the effects of the geometric nonlinearity of the MMB test apparatus. This analysis used an iterative approach, and the first step was to choose an applied load, P_a . (To calculate fracture toughness, this applied load would be the critical load measured during an MMB test.) This loading was then used to calculate the initial loading which would exist on the undeformed specimen. This specimen loading was used with linear beam theory to calculate the deformed shape of the specimen. The deformation of the specimen caused the lever to rotate and displace and its new position was calculated. The rotation of the lever caused a horizontal component of applied load to develop due to the roller loading which always acts normal to the lever surface. The loading on the specimen was recalculated using the new lever loading and position. The next iteration was begun by recalculating the deformed shaped of the specimen from the specimen loading. The iterative process was repeated until the change in the lever rotation from one iteration to the next was negligible.

The nonlinear analysis was shown in reference 4 to accurately predict the load displacement response of MMB tests. The excellent agreement of the analysis with measured displacements indicates that the analysis should also accurately calculate the strain energy release rate of the MMB specimen. The equations in reference 4 used to calculate G included corrections for rotations about the crack tip[7] and shear deformation[6,8] as has been done for the pure mode tests.

$$(G_I)_{nl} = \frac{M_I^2}{bE_{11}I} \left(1 + \frac{2}{\lambda a} + \frac{1}{(\lambda a)^2} \right) + \frac{6(P_I)^2}{5b^2G_{12}h} \quad (1)$$

$$(G_{II})_{nl} = \frac{3M_{II}^2}{4bE_{11}I} + \frac{9(P_{II})^2}{80b^2G_{12}h} \quad \text{where } \lambda = \frac{1}{h} \sqrt{\frac{6E_{22}}{E_{11}}} \quad (2)$$

M_I and M_{II} are the moments symmetrically and antisymmetrically occurring at the crack tip, respectively, and the terms P_I and P_{II} correspond to the loading that would be applied to the specimen to obtain a pure mode I (DCB) or a pure mode II (ENF) test. These loadings are determined from the iterative nonlinear analysis.

The linear analysis developed in reference 3 is used to compare with the nonlinear analysis. This analysis assumes that there is no change in loading due to specimen deformation, and the calculation of G is therefore much simpler since the equations can be written in terms of the initial applied load P_a .

$$(G_I)_{lin} = \frac{4P_a^2(3c-L)^2}{64bL^2E_{11}I} \left[a^2 + \frac{2a}{\lambda} + \frac{1}{\lambda^2} + \frac{h^2E_{11}}{10G_{12}} \right] \quad (3)$$

$$(G_{II})_{lin} = \frac{3P_a^2(c+L)^2}{64bL^2E_{11}I} \left[a^2 + \frac{h^2E_{11}}{5G_{12}} \right] \quad (4)$$

5. REDESIGN OF THE MMB APPARATUS

The nonlinear analysis showed that the errors caused by using linear theory to calculate G could be as large as 30% which is unacceptably large. Because it would be inconvenient to use a nonlinear analysis to analyze MMB data, the MMB apparatus was redesigned to minimize the nonlinearity so that a linear analysis could be used. As previously mentioned, the nonlinearity was primarily due to the change in the direction of the applied lever load. The applied load, which was initially vertical, developed a horizontal component as the lever rotated as seen in figure 2. This horizontal force tended to significantly reduce the strain energy release rate of the test specimen. The obvious solution to the nonlinearity problem was therefore to eliminate the horizontal force. This horizontal force can be eliminated by simply attaching the roller to the lever and loading the roller with a horizontal surface attached to the load machine. Since the surface on which the roller bears no longer rotates, the reaction on the lever will remain vertical.

However, when the roller is attached to the lever, it moves horizontally as the lever rotates about the hinge pin. This causes the horizontal distance from the hinge to change, as shown by Δc in figure 3(a). The changing load location changes the moment about the hinge pin, causing a geometric nonlinearity. This effect is reduced as the height of the roller above the specimen midplane is reduced, as shown in figure 3(b). Figure 4 shows how the errors due to this nonlinearity change with roller height. The errors in the mode I and mode II G components are presented as a percentage of the total G as was done in reference 4. At a load-point height, v , of 15 mm (0.6 in.) the nonlinearity error is approximately $\pm 2\%$. These results were calculated for a toughness of $G_c = 1.75 \text{ kJ/m}^2$ (10 in-lb/in²) with the graphite/PEEK test specimen described earlier. The results are also valid for tests on other materials such as glass/epoxy having a different modulus, provided the specimens have a comparable bending stiffness ($E_{11}I$).

Figure 3.- Effect of lever height on load point translation (a) original height. (b) lower height.

Figure 4.- Effect of load-point height above specimen mid-plane on G error.

The MMB apparatus was redesigned to have a load-point height of 15 mm (0.6 in) so that the nonlinearity error will be small when a linear analysis is used to analyze the MMB test data. This design required a saddle-like device so that the lever did not contact the specimen during loading. The saddle extends down on both sides of the lever and the test specimen, as shown in figure 5. The saddle holds one bearing on each side of the lever such that the top of the bearing is at 15 mm (0.6 in.) above the mid-plane of the specimen. The apparatus is loaded with a yoke which contacts the rollers without touching the lever. The lever length and therefore the mixed-mode ratio is changed by moving the saddle along the lever.

Figure 5.- Redesigned MMB apparatus.

Figure 6.- Load-point displacement response of an APC2 split beam specimen in the redesigned MMB apparatus.

Figure 6 shows load-displacement curves measured with the redesigned apparatus when the lever lengths were set to produce the 4/1, 1/1, and 1/4 mixed-mode conditions. These experimentally measured curves agree closely with the linear analysis calculations. G errors due to nonlinearity can be seen in figure.7 where percent error is plotted versus delamination length. From this figure, it can be seen that for a material as tough as 1.75 kJ/m^2 (10 in-lb/in^2) the G errors are less than about $\pm 2\%$ as the delamination grows over the test region.

Figure 7.- Error in G calculation for the redesigned MMB test.

Figure 8 shows G errors due to nonlinearity for a range of G_c values with $a = 45\text{mm}$. These nonlinearity errors are less than about $\pm 3\%$ for materials with G_c as high as 3.5 kJ/m^2 (20 in-lb/in^2). Therefore, the redesigned MMB apparatus will have nonlinearity errors that are acceptably small even for materials twice as tough as APC2, provided the specimen bending stiffness is at least as large as that used in this study.

Figure 8.- Error in G calculation for varying material toughness.

6. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

The APC2 toughness testing in reference 3 was conducted with the original MMB apparatus, a linear analysis, and a 4/1 precrack. Results from reference 3 are shown as open circles in figure 9. However, these data points are slightly different from those previously presented in reference 3 because the critical load was redefined to be the maximum load from the load-displacement curve instead of the load where the slope changes abruptly. This change in critical load resulted in only minor shifts in the G_c data which are now comparable to those in the present study. The results from reference 3 were also reanalyzed using the nonlinear analysis and are shown as filled circles and by the dashed line in figure 9. Notice that the G_I/G_{II} ratios have changed and that, as predicted, all the G values calculated using the nonlinear analysis are lower than the linear values.

The toughness measurements made with the redesigned apparatus and the linear analysis are presented in figure 9 as open squares and a dash-dot line. These results should agree with the data from the previous study, but as shown in this figure, the redesigned data (dash-dot line) lie below those from the original apparatus (dashed line). This discrepancy is believed to be due to material differences. Note that the average G_{Ic} changed from 1.26 kJ/m^2 (7.2 in-lb/in^2) for the previous study to 0.96 kJ/m^2 (5.5 in-lb/in^2) for the present study even though the mode I, DCB test and the analysis were identical for the two studies. Furthermore, the flexural modulus changed from 116 GPa (16.8 Msi) for the previous study to 129 GPa (18.7 Msi) in the present study. Since G_{Ic} and G_{IIc} are inversely related to the modulus, as seen in equations 3 and 4, this change in modulus may also contribute to the discrepancy in toughness between the two studies. These material differences can probably be attributed to processing[9,10]. Since the data from both studies can be modeled with straight lines that have similar slopes, the fracture toughness measurements from the redesigned MMB apparatus and a simple linear analysis are believed to be accurate. The linear curve fit agrees with the following failure criterion suggested in references 11 and 12.

$$\frac{G_I}{G_{Ic}} + \frac{G_{II}}{G_{IIc}} = 1 \quad (9)$$

Figure 9.- Mixed-mode interlaminar fracture toughness of APC2 with 4/1 mixed-mode ratio precrack. ($1 \text{ kJ/m}^2 = 5.71 \text{ in-lb/in}^2$)

7. CONCLUDING REMARKS

The MMB test uses a lever to simultaneously apply mode I and mode II loading to a split-beam specimen. A nonlinear, iterative analysis had shown that the measured delamination fracture toughness of tough materials may have large errors when linear beam theory is used to analyze the test data. The MMB loading apparatus has therefore been redesigned to virtually eliminate the nonlinearities. A complex nonlinear analysis is, therefore, no longer needed to analyze MMB data. The analysis showed that an optimum design was achieved when the MMB loading was applied through a roller which is attached to the lever so that the roller contact height is 15 mm (0.6 in.) above the specimen mid-plane. With the redesigned MMB apparatus, the errors due to the nonlinearity are less than $\pm 3\%$ for the APC2 specimen used in this study, and hence, can be ignored. Similarly small errors should be expected for other materials, provided the specimen bending stiffness is at least as large as that used in the present study.

The delamination fracture toughness of APC2 was measured with the redesigned apparatus and compared to results found earlier using the original apparatus. After the previous data were reanalyzed using the nonlinear analysis, they exhibited a trend similar to redesigned MMB data analyzed with the linear analysis. The difference in toughness between the previous study and the present study was attributed to manufacturing differences in the material. Therefore, using the redesigned MMB apparatus, mixed-mode delamination fracture toughness can be calculated from test data using a simple linear beam theory.

8. REFERENCES

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